

NOTES

TABLE 1 - PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF AMINO ACIDS

Sl. no.	Properties	Product obtained						
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
1.	R _f value in (%)							
	(i) BAW	8.5	10.5	16.4	19.5	23.1	29.0	30.5
	(ii) BAPW	25.4	33.8	41.0	45.2	50.2	53.2	56.2
2.	Colour with ^a							
	(i) Ninhydrin	R	V	BV	RV	V	V	BV
	(ii) Isatin	-	BP	B	P	PB	BP	BP
	(iii) Folin's reagent	Y	B	G	GBr	GBr	G	GBr
3.	DNP Dvts.							
	(i) R _f value (%) ^b	-	-	12.0	36.1	-	50.7	-
	(ii) M.p. (°C)	-	-	186	202	-	177	-
4.	Fluorescence in uv black light lamp ^a	-	BW	W	W	BW	W	BW
5.	Co-chromatography one spot with amino acid	-	Orn	Asp	Gly	Threo	α-Ala	β-Ala
6.	Amino acid identified	-	Orn	Asp	Gly	Threo	α-Ala	β-Ala

^aV = Violet, B = blue, R = red, P = pink, G = green, Gr = grey, Br = brown, W = white, Y = yellow.

^bR_f in tert-amyl alcohol - 3% ammonia, 1 : 1, v/v at 16 ± 2°.

BAW solvent system : 1-butanol - acetic acid - water, 4 : 1 : 5, v/v ; upper layer.

BAPW solvent system : 1-butanol - acetic acid - pyridine - water, 15 : 3 : 10 : 12, v/v at 16 ± 2°.

of sunlight irradiation in aqueous solution of lysine in presence and absence of different additives are recorded in Table 2. It was observed that the effect of different additives used was in the order : urea > lysine > magnesium phosphate > ammonium sulphate > diammonium hydrogen phosphate, keeping in view the destruction of lysine. Out of the seven compounds, six have been characterised as ornithine (II), aspartic acid (III), glycine (IV), threonine (V), α-alanine (VI) and β-alanine (VII).

TABLE 2 - RESULTS OF SUNLIGHT IRRADIATION (40 h) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF LYSINE UNDER HETEROGENOUS CONDITIONS

Reaction mixture*	Products formed**						
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Lys + W	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
Lys + W + Mgp	++	+	+	-	+	-	+
Lys + W + DAp	-	-	T	T	-	-	-
Lys + W + AS	-	++	+	+	-	+	+
Lys + W + U	+++	-	+	+	-	-	+

*W = Water, Mgp = magnesium phosphate, DAp = diammonium hydrogen phosphate, AS = ammonium sulphate, U = urea. **T = Traces, (-) = not detected, (+) = fair yield, (++) = good yield, (+++) = high yield.

Morokuma¹ exposed lysine-HCl, dissolved in 4% Na₂CO₃ or 4% HCl to ultraviolet rays for 10 h and by chromatographic analysis revealed the formation of aspartic acid, glutamic acid, γ-amino-adipic acid, glycine, alanine, norvaline, norleucine and cadaverine. Thus the present study of sunlight initiated changes in aqueous solution of lysine in the presence or absence of additives shows interesting results as compared to the ultraviolet irradiation by Morokuma. While some of the amino

acids formed are the same others differ in their identity.

References

1. C. PONNAMPERUMA and E. PETERSON, *Radiation Res*, 1966, 3, 27.
2. T. MOROKUMA, *Chem. Abstr*, 1955, 49, 4051
3. C. PONNAMPERUMA and E. PETERSON, *Science*, 1965, 147, 1572.
4. C. J. FLORES and C. PONNAMPERUMA, *J. Mol. Evolution*, 1972, 2, 1
5. H. D. PATHAK and K. S. KHETWAL, *Indian J. Biochem*, 1970, 7, 211.
6. R. CRUICKSHANK, "A Text Book of Modern Microbiology", Churchill Livingstone, 1975, pp. 2, 58.
7. E. STAHL, "Thin-Layer Chromatography", Springer, Berlin, 1969, 730.
8. K. S. KHETWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 58, 1028.

Synthesis of Substituted Aromatic Amides

SUNITA SHARMA**, ARVINDER KAUR
and
M. S. BHATIA*

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University,
Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 31 October 1988, revised 6 June 1989,
accepted 20 June 1989

HETEROAROMATICS, amide linkage, unsaturation and cyano group have been cited in literature as important functionalities for enhancing herbicidal activity¹. Vasilev and Terebenina² synthesised 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-halobenzoyl-pyra-

**Department of Entomology.

zol-5-ones and tested for herbicidal activity and plant growth regulating activity. Zharasov³ found that pre-plant application of mixture of trichloroacetic acid, phenazone and hexilure controlled weeds and increased yield of sugarbeet crops and increased sugar content also. Some biologically important α -cyanoalkylidene acetamides have been found to be active against rice, berley and wheat⁴.

In the present communication, *N*-[4(2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolen-5-one)yl]-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (2), *N*-cyclohexyl-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (3) and *N*-(tetrahydro-1,4-oxazin)yl-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (4) have been synthesised by

reacting 2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid with 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one, cyclohexylamine and morpholine respectively. The acid (1) was, in turn, prepared by Knoevengael reaction between cyanoacetic acid and 2-methoxybenzaldehyde. The compounds were characterised by ¹H nmr and mass spectral data. The nmr spectra^{6,7} of 2 and 3 exhibited signals at δ 7.1–8.4 (NH, confirmed by D₂O exchange), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 9.1 (1H, s, CH=C). The aromatic protons resonated in the range δ 7.1–7.8 as multiplet. In addition, 2 showed singlets at δ 2.4 (O=C–C=C–CH₃) and 3.3 (NCH₃). In 3 methylenic protons of cyclohexyl group appeared as multiplets in the range δ 1.1–2.2. 4 showed singlet at δ 3.9 (OCH₃). Multiplets at δ 8.35, 7.7 and 3.7 were observed due to HC=C, four aromatic protons and eight methylenic protons of morpholine respectively.

Mass spectra of 2 showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 202 (17%), 201 (19%), 186 (12%), 169 (100%), 125 (12%), 107 (7%) and 54 (35%). 3 exhibited prominent peaks at *m/z* 257 (71%), 241 (99%), 227(26%), 186 (100%), 158 (22%), 156 (36%), 128 (28%), 107 (26%), 92 (36%) and 77(44%).

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra were taken on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectrometer

and mass spectra on a Jeol-JMS-D-300 spectrometer (70 eV) with JMA-2000 data processing unit.

2-Cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid: To a mixture of 2-methoxybenzaldehyde (7.0 g) and cyanoacetic acid (5.0 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 ml), was added perchloric acid (70%, 15 ml) and the mixture kept for 48 h at 25°. The reddish brown precipitate was decomposed in crushed ice. The resulting solid product was crystallised from ethanol to obtain 1 (6.0 g, 49%), m.p. 201–11° (Found: C, 65.00; H, 4.40. C₁₁H₉NO₃ calcd. for: C, 65.02; H, 4.43%).

***N*-[4-(2,3-Dimethyl-1'-phenylpyrazolen-5-one)yl]-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (2):** A solution of phosphorus oxychloride (0.76 g) was added dropwise to an ice-cold well-stirred solution of 2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid (1; 1.01 g), triethylamine (0.17 g) and 4-aminophenazone (1.01 g) in dry dichloromethane (50 ml). Then additional triethylamine (0.34 g) was added in one instalment. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1/2 h at 0° and further 8 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was decomposed in crushed-ice and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml). The organic portion was washed with saturated solution of sodium carbonate, water, hydrochloric acid (10%) and finally with water. The organic portion was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the organic residue purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform mixture (1:3) as eluent to yield 2 (10 g, 51%), (Found: C, 68.02; H, 5.12. C₂₂H₂₀N₄O₅ calcd. for: C, 68.04, H, 5.15%).

***N*-Cyclohexyl-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (3):** The acid (1; 1.01 g) was treated with triethylamine (0.51 g), cyclohexylamine (0.50 g), phosphorus oxychloride (0.77 g) in dry dichloromethane (100 ml) as detailed to obtain the amide to yield 4 (66%), m.p. 217–19° (Found: C, 71.80; H, 7.02. C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 71.83, H, 7.04%).

***N*-(Tetrahydro-1,4-oxazin)yl-2-cyano-3-(2'-methoxy-1'-phenyl)acrylamide (4):** The acid (1; 1.01 g) was treated with triethylamine (0.51 g) in dry dichloromethane (100 ml) as detailed to obtain the amide to yield 4 (66%), m.p. 217–19° (Found: C, 66.15; H, 5.86; N, 10.27. C₁₅H₁₆N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 66.17; H, 5.88; N, 10.29%).

References

1. M. M. SIDDIQUI and V. R. CHAKRAVAR, *J. Maharashtra Agric. Univ.*, 1979, 4, 123.
2. C. VASILEV and A. TERE BENINA, *Dokl. Bolg. Akad. Nauk*, 1981, 34, 391.
3. S. U. ZHARASOV, *Khim. Selsk. Khoz.*, 1982, 14, 30.
4. N. KEMICHI, S. MEMORU, H. KIMISKI, Y. KAZOMOM, NAOLO and T. KAZUO, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1985, 49, 3023, 28.

5. J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1969, p. 147.
6. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSELM, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1967.
7. A. BOVEY and B. FRANK, "NMR Data Tables for Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1967, Vol. I.
8. Q. N. PORTER and J. BELDAR, "Mass Spectrometry of Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1971, p. 549.
9. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, H. C. DJERASSI and D. H. WILLIAMS, "Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds", Holden Day, London, 1967, p. 669.

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted-phenyl) [(substituted-phenyl)azo]methylene]hydrazides as Possible Anthelmintics

M. IMTIAZ HUSAIN* and VINAY KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 6 March 1989, revised 6 June 1989,
accepted 20 June 1989

A number of compounds with benzothiazole as parent nucleus are known to possess various biological activities including anthelmintic activity¹. Recently, hydrazides² and azo compounds³ have also been used in the therapy of helminthiasis. These observations prompted us to synthesise the title compounds as per Scheme 1 with a view to evaluate their anthelmintic efficacy.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid hydrazide: It was prepared according to the reported procedure⁴.

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazides: These compounds were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of (2-benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid hydrazide and substituted-benzaldehyde in methanol for 5 h. The solid separated was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no.**	R ₁	R ₂	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1. ^a	NO ₂	H	166	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
2. ^b	OH	OCH ₃	108	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
3.	H	Cl	122	77	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl

*N analysis found satisfactory for all compounds
**ν_{max}: ^a3 420 (NH), 1 680 (amide C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 530 (NO₂); ^b3 420 (NH), 1 680 (amide C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH).

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	NO ₂	H	4-Cl	146	84	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
2.	NO ₂	H	3-NO ₂	150	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
3.	NO ₂	H	4-NO ₂	153	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
4.	NO ₂	H	4-COOH	148	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
5.	NO ₂	H	4-CH ₃	147	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂
6. ^a	NO ₂	H	4-OH	151	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
7.	OH	OCH ₃	4-Cl	102	81	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
8.	OH	OCH ₃	3-NO ₂	98	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
9. ^b	OH	OCH ₃	4-NO ₂	65	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
10.	OH	OCH ₃	4-COOH	95	67	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
11.	OH	OCH ₃	4-CH ₃	108	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂
12.	OH	OCH ₃	4 OH	116	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
13.	H	Cl	3-NO ₂	78	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
14.	H	Cl	4-Cl	140	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl ₂
15.	H	Cl	4-COOH	137	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
16.	H	Cl	2-OH	138	81	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
17.	H	Cl	4-NO ₂	135	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Cl
18.	H	Cl	4-CH ₃	134	61	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl

*N analysis found satisfactory for all the compounds; Compounds sl. nos. 2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 15, 16 and 17 screened for anthelmintic activity. **ν_{max}: ^a1 680 (CO), 3 500 (OH), 1 610 (N=N) and 1 530 (NO₂); ^b1 680 (CO), 3 420 (NH), 1 610 (N=N) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted-phenyl) [(substituted-phenyl)azo]methylene]hydrazides: To sodium nitrite (0.02 mol) dissolved in water and cooled to 0°, was added to an ice-cold solution of an aromatic amine (0.015 mol) in concentrated HCl. The mixture was poured into a cold solution of (2-benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid